

ISic0976

I.Sicily inscription 0976

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140453

1. Ούλπια[νή],
2. ἡ ἀξία μ[ου],
3. ἔζησεν ἔ[τη —],
4. μῆνες ι', [ἡμέ]-
5. ρες ι [(.)]²⁷η[(.)]; κ[(.)]²⁷.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492602

EDCS 39102129

PHI 140453

Bibliography

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